

NEXUS: A Tangible Multi-User Sensor-Based Telematic Novel Mixing-Interface for Multimedial Exploration

HannaH “Vyborg” Walter*
hannah.walter@zhdk.ch
Institute for Computer Music and
Sound Technology
Zurich University of the Arts
Zurich, Switzerland
Mycelium
Bern, Switzerland

Eric Larrieux*
eric.larrieux@zhdk.ch
Institute for Computer Music and
Sound Technology
Immersive Arts Space
Zurich University of the Arts
Zurich, Switzerland

Robert Toche
robert@worldingmycelium.space
Mycelium
Bern, Switzerland

Cedric Spindler
cedric.spindler@fhnw.ch
Academy of Music
University of Applied Sciences and
Arts Northwestern Switzerland
Basel, Switzerland

Patrick Müller
patrick.mueller@zhdk.ch
Institute for Computer Music and
Sound Technology
Zurich, Switzerland

Figure 1: Robert Torche as mixing engineer performing within the *NEXUS* at Usinesonore Festival, La Neuveville, June 4, 2024. ©Usinesonore, photo by Cyrille Voirol

*Both authors contributed equally to this research.

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Abstract

This paper explores the realm of telematic performance practice, interconnecting geographically disparate locations and performers through telecommunication technologies. Specifically, we focus on networked multimedia mixing and advance the field within the framework of third-wave human-computer interaction, emphasizing embodied interaction. Along with a detailed introduction of our Novel Interface for Multimedial Exploration, the *NEXUS*, we provide insights into our first use-case scenario, employing

the NEXUS-NIME within a telematic performance context. Adapting and expanding on existing examples of dimension spaces, we introduce a novel *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction*, which accounts for situated embodiment. It is employed in a dimension space analysis comparing the NEXUS with historical interfaces for networked musical and multimedial expression that incorporate multimodal interactions through tangible user interfaces. In doing so we demonstrate the NEXUS's role as a transformative multi-user tool and bundle of NIMes, shifting sound engineering practices from one of *transparency* and *social fidelity* to one of *hypermediacy*, *risk* and *respons-ability*. Drawing on concepts from feminist new materialism and posthumanism, the NEXUS opens new avenues for *rendering-capable*, for exploring complex interdependencies between human and non-human actors *becoming-with* in telematic ecosystems.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; *Media arts*; *Performing arts*; • **Human-centered computing** → *Sound-based input / output*; *Mixed / augmented reality*; **Collaborative interaction**.

Keywords

Telematic performance, New Interfaces for Musical Expression, Human-Computer Interaction, embodied interaction, dimension space analysis, networked multimedia mixing, posthumanism, tangible user interfaces, digital musical instrument, extended reality, mixed reality, digital augmentation, responsive environments, sonic interaction design, embedded systems, feminist new materialism.

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1 Introduction

Telematic performances connect heterogeneous spaces across multiple locations via telecommunication technologies, allowing distant participants to interact in a performative situation in near real time. A wide variety of artistic practices have emerged and evolved with the advent and ever increasing ubiquity of the internet in the fields of music, theatre, dance and performance art. Müller et al. propose a classifying framework for organizing the variety of dimensions at play in telematic performance practices as a bundle of telematic NIMes (*Novel X for Multimedial Exploration*), in which the variable ‘X’ is typically replaced by [Interface], but may also be [Instrument, Media, Network, or Space] [30]. The format intrinsically engenders a high level of mediation, as distant sounds, visuals, and bodies have to be represented on a local stage in order to make performer interactions possible and audience experience legible. Positioned at the nexus of the data pathway between local and remote stages is the mediating agent: the live multimedia mixing engineer, whose practice with the media mixing console is critical to the transmission and mediation process.

In this study, we specifically focus on designing for this human-machine interface in the context of networked multimedia mixing, developing what we call the NEXUS. Our work advances the field by adopting a third-wave human-computer interaction framework, which emphasizes the principles of embodied interaction [8], [20], [19]. We provide a detailed account of the instrument's design, followed by some insights from our first use-case scenario, the telematic kompost*klang*küche* NEXUS-NIME. To facilitate a comparative visual analysis of the instrument's design, we employ a *dimension space analysis*, adapting and expanding on existing examples of dimension spaces to introduce a *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction*. Our analytical approach integrates historical and foundational references to evaluate our interface design and reveals critical aspects of interaction design that are often overlooked in traditional frameworks. Through this lens, we examine how embodied interaction, contextual sensitivity, and the interplay between transparency and opacity shape the role of the mixing performer in the telematic NEXUS-NIME.

2 Audio Mixing Interfaces. State of the Art

Braasch et al. highlight the importance of developing specialized mixing consoles for telematic acoustic musicking. Through their proposition of a software-based prototype mixer programmed in Max/MSP, they aim to achieve spatial continuity in creating a shared virtual space between local and remote environments. To this end, the authors have enhanced the traditional fader-based sound mixing console design by integrating additional modules crucial for homogeneous spatial configurations in telematic projects, such as latency meters, remote data links, auralization units, remote sound level calibration units, remote monitoring, and synchronized remote audio-recording units. Beyond the development of networked mixing consoles featuring mirrored functionalities to facilitate remote access (and thereby transforming the mixing process into a collaborative multi-user activity), the conventional interface design, a mixing desk characterized by its potentiometer- and fader-based controls, maintains the original interaction paradigm without revision [6]. Several systems have reconceptualized the traditional mixing console's channel strip control mechanisms, employing what is referred to as the *stage metaphor* [17] to manage music mixing [17], [9], [16]. These innovations include the incorporation of multi-touch surface technologies ([27], [9], [16]) and tangible user interface (TUI) control schemes [16].

Gelineck et al.'s combination of a digital abstract representation on the multi-touch table with tangible object manipulation (TUI blocks)¹ offers a promising solution to the absence of tactile feedback in earlier multi-touch systems. The primary affordances of these developments include intuitiveness, playfulness, and inclusivity, which collectively diminish the level of expertise required to operate the interface [16].

The embodiment of the mixing engineer remains consistent whether interfacing with a traditional analog or digital mixing console, characterized by physical sliders, knobs, and buttons, or a tangible multi-touch system equipped with physical objects (e.g.

¹Gelineck et al.'s music mixing interface draws inspiration from the *reacTable* [22]. For further exploration of tabletop tangible interfaces (TTIs) in music performance, including the challenges and opportunities they present for beginners and experts in collaborative musical practice, see [40].

TUI blocks). In accordance with Bongers’s taxonomy for physical interface design, the spatial influence from a human-scale perspective remains categorized as “*intimate* (isometric / 0 - 10 cm), close to the body,” in this case “within the hand.” [3, p. 163]. With the interface presented in this paper, we expand the range of the mixing interface into “the architectural, or spatial, body movement [with a] locomotion and location in space [of] 0 - 10 metre” [3, p. 163].

3 NEXUS Instrument Design

In developing what we term the *NEXUS Telematic Novel Mixing-Interface for Multimedial Exploration*, we approached the mixing interface design process with a focus on embodied human-computer-world interaction. The transition from modern to contemporary human-computer interface (HCI)² has been marked by several significant turns, exemplified by what is referred to as the third paradigm in HCI [20]. The turn to embodiment is rooted in the philosophical traditions of phenomenology, particularly the works of Heidegger [21] and Merleau-Ponty [28]. In the *Phenomenology of Perception*, Merleau-Ponty emphasizes that we engage with the world through a *lived body* (*le corps propre*) [29], a perspective which challenges the Cartesian mind-body dualism by asserting that perception is an active, embodied process where the lived body is central to our interaction with the environment and the co-construction of meaning.

Building on this foundation, Dourish applied phenomenology and social science as the theoretical basis for his discussion on social and tangible computing [12]. Extending Dourish’s work, Svanæs introduces the concept of *kinaesthetic creativity*, highlighting the body’s ability to engage directly and creatively with the *feel* dimension of interactive systems [36]. Svanæs argues that active bodily engagement in the design process often sparks innovative ideas that “originate ‘from the body;’” cautioning that “the best way to kill creativity is by remaining seated on chairs around a table” [36, p. 8].

Grounding the design of the *NEXUS* in these embodied principles, we aim to create a media mixing interface that moves beyond the constraints of traditional tabletop contexts. Our approach is intended to amplify the creative capacities of the users (the mixing performers), enabling them to engage with the telematic ecosystem in a more intuitive, embodied, and meaningful manner.

3.1 Embodied Interaction Approach to Multimedia Mixing in Telematic NIMES

In order to design for the embodied interaction among users, tools, and contexts, we assembled an interdisciplinary research team that comprises composer-performers, sound designers, digital luthiers, and electrical engineers. This collaborative effort is part of a joint research project between *Worlding Mycelium* and the *Telematic Performance Format Group (TPF)* research unit at the Zurich University of the Art’s Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology (ICST).

Given that our project is primarily embedded within the specific socio-cultural context of telematic performance practices, the design objectives were structured as follows:

- a) To give physical form to the seemingly virtual world of the telecommunication network, thus materializing the intermediary space between geographically distant locations;
- b) To heighten awareness among users — including both local and remote performers, as well as the audience — of the medium and the media mixing engineer, revealing their agency in the socio-cultural network and thereby exploring the meaning of the interface through its *opacity* or *hypermediacy* (as discussed by Bolter [2]);
- c) To create an interactive *architectural space* (as discussed by Bongers [3]) serving as mixing interface in which the practice of the mixing engineers are made visible to colleagues and audience. In this context, the mixing engineer transforms into a performer, embodying the figure of the media “messenger” [25], centrally positioned in the transmission of communications between distant spaces and entities.

Our initial approach to designing the *NEXUS* utilized tangible computing principles (as discussed by Dourish [12]) to transition from a symbolic representation of space (see mixing stage metaphor in Section 2) into a physical form. Drawing on Fishkin’s *metaphor of noun* approach of the taxonomy of tangible interfaces [13], we developed an analogy that informs the novel tangible design of the *NEXUS* mixing device. In this analogy, the metaphorical space of the World Wide Web conceived as the *global network of data streams* is represented in the physical world by a web of strings within a scaled-down version of a half-sphere model of planet earth, a hemispherical geodesic dome with a web of sensing lines strung throughout it.³ Multiple media mixing performers operate and mix audio and video data streams on suspended sensing lines in the middle of this tangible, *half-globe-net* instrument.

The physical representation of the net, which is “composed not only of strings but also of the gaps between the strings” [1, p. 6] (referring to [7]) and the precarious nature of performing and balancing on suspended sensing lines, not only facilitate the performers’ interaction, but also serve as a critique of the idealized image of the World Wide Web as an equally distributed and accessible network. Contemporary discourse has increasingly problematized this ideal, highlighting critical issues such as digital divides, unequal access to information [31], and the centralization of control [15], which collectively challenge the notion of an open and egalitarian digital space. Thus, with the *NEXUS* we transform the traditional mixing console into a tangible material-semiotic web.

The following presentation of the technical overview for our tangible multi-user sensor-based Telematic Novel Mixing-Interface for Multimedial Exploration is divided into several key components. Initially, the design of the sensing system is detailed, followed by a description of its integration into the TUI, before concluding with a summary of how this system is integrated within the broader telematic NIME framework.

³For the construction of this tangible artifact, we collaborated with Dominik Ziliotis, the founder of *Livingdome*, who designed and built a 2v geodesic dome with a diameter of 3.5 meters and a height of 1.75 meters. This structure, akin to the size of children’s climbing domes, is crafted from wooden rods, wooden dowels, and leather connections. The materials used (wood, leather, wax, wool, and hemp) ensure that the structure is both lightweight for mobility and highly stable [41]. The organic design and material choices align with our need for a durable yet portable construction suitable for the *NEXUS* installation. For more information, visit *Livingdome* <https://www.livingdome.com/index.php>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

²For a comprehensive overview of the past and present theoretical developments in HCI, see [33].

3.2 Sensing System Design

The sensing system is composed of three primary sub-systems: the sensing elements, coupling and mounting hardware, and the embedded system. These components are described in the subsections below.

3.2.1 Sensing Elements. The sensing sub-system is built around a pair of generic load cells and an HX711 amplifier and analog-to-digital converter circuit. This combination is commonly used in both commercial products, such as bathroom scales, as well as a wide variety of DIY electronic projects, and thus many tutorials are available online.⁴

Each load cell contains strain gauge and a fixed resistor arranged as a voltage divider affixed to a metal frame. Wired together they form a full Wheatstone bridge⁵ which is capable of measuring the change in resistance in the strain gauge caused by its deformation. This configuration has the advantage of both being sensitive with minimal drift, while also offering a large operating range. The load cells we used were rated for up to 50 kg each, so in our case we are able to reliably sense loads of up to 100 kg. The resulting signal is amplified and converted to a 24-bit digital value by the HX711 ADC circuit⁶ before being transferred to the microcontroller via a serial connection (as described in Section 3.2.3). It is worth noting that quality issues with our batch of HX711 circuits seem to cause noisy and erratic data at times, particularly when powering the embedded system via its USB-C input (we suspect this is due to possible current limiting issues stemming from the quick charge feature of the USB-C protocol).

3.2.2 Coupling Hardware. All hardware was designed specifically for this application through an iterative design and testing process. The coupling plate is composed of a three-layer stack of 120 mm square plates. The top and bottom layer were laser cut of 3 mm thick steel, while a 6 mm thick MDF plate in the middle supports the two load cells, as detailed in Figure 2. The stack is compressed by the weight of the performer on the sensor line which pulls through its center compressing it against the outside of a node on the dome, thus transferring the force to the two load cells between the steel plates (as indicated by the downward arrow in Figure 3). This action is facilitated by an additional gap of approximately 2 mm between the middle and top plates as well as cutouts in the bottom steel plate (see Figure 4b), which allow the center portion of the load cells to temporarily deform when compressed by the top plate.

A 3D printed fixture was designed to attach the microcontroller and interfacing electronics to the top of the mounting plate stack, as shown in Figures 2, 3, and 4a. The load cells are connected to the HX711 via screw terminals, and the HX711 to the microcontroller by a Grove connector (see Figure 4a). As the system should be robust and withstand unpredictable performance environments, a 120 x 120 x 3 mm acrylic glass plate is affixed to the top plate via

50 mm standoffs to shield the delicate electronic components from accidental damage.⁷

Figure 2: Exploded view of 3D model of sensor unit.

3.2.3 Embedded System Design. The embedded system at the heart of the sensing module is implemented on a M5StickC PLUS ESP32-PICO Mini IoT Development Kit⁸ using the Arduino programming environment. It comprises two main modules: the load cell interface system and the data transmission system, which are managed by the HX711.h⁹ and PubSubClient.h¹⁰ libraries, respectively.

Normal scale operation (setup, measurement, display, taring, and calibration) was implemented as described in the SCALES_KIT.ino example provided as part of the M5StickCPlus Arduino library,¹¹ but the calibration result is saved to and loaded from memory,

⁴e.g. <https://circuitjournal.com/50kg-load-cells-with-HX711>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wheatstone_bridge, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

⁶https://cdn.sparkfun.com/datasheets/Sensors/ForceFlex/hx711_english.pdf, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

⁷The full hardware design can be found here: <https://cad.onshape.com/documents/6e9dfbaf1ed5f7ae724d6e1/w/318b9f56b268b79ff310bd4e/e/f3283beca219b94027c61e29>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

⁸https://docs.m5stack.com/en/core/m5stickc_plus, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

⁹<https://github.com/bogde/HX711>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

¹⁰<https://github.com/knolleary/pubsubclient>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

¹¹https://github.com/m5stack/M5StickC-Plus/blob/master/examples/KIT/SCALES_KIT/SCALES_KIT.ino, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

Figure 3: Assembled view of 3D model of sensor unit. The arrow indicates how the slack sensor line compresses the sensor stack when under load.

(a) Front view.

(b) Rear view.

Figure 4: Images of sensor unit.

as detailed in the EEPROM.ino example file.¹² It is worth noting that although it is not shown in the example file, EEPROM.commit() needs to be called in order for data to persist in memory after power off on ESP32 based devices such as the M5StickC Plus. The resulting load cell data (force value and sensor ID) was published at a rate of 10 Hz using the MQTT messaging protocol¹³ to an instance of the shiftr.io cloud service.¹⁴ The transmission procedure over WiFi was implemented as detailed in MQTT.ino example file included with the M5StickC Plus library.¹⁵

¹²<https://github.com/m5stack/M5StickC-Plus/blob/master/examples/Advanced/Storage/EEPROM/EEPROM.ino>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

¹³MQTT is a lightweight, publish-subscribe network protocol that enables devices to communicate with each other with low bandwidth usage, making it ideal for various Internet of Things (IoT) applications.

¹⁴<https://www.shiftr.io>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

¹⁵<https://github.com/m5stack/M5StickC-Plus/blob/master/examples/Advanced/MQTT/MQTT.ino>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

3.3 Sensing System Integration

The sensing system integration process consisted of the testing and iteration of the overall hardware design, sensor calibration, and integrating the sensor lines into the dome, and is detailed in the subsections below.

3.3.1 Design Testing and Evolution. In the initial design, the sensor stack was suspended from a hub on the inside of the geodesic dome by a system of four metal cables attached to eye bolts that passed through the bottom plate; the sensor line was attached to an eye bolt that passed through the plate in the opposite direction, allowing it to compress the load cells (see Figure 5). While this configuration ensured that the sensor plate stack remained orthogonal to the direction of applied force from the slack line as it flexed, guaranteeing maximally accurate readings, it was not ideal, as it also reduced the usable area of the sensor lines by around 50 cm and was dangerous for the performer (and potentially the sensors themselves).

After several iterations of testing and simplifying modifications of the design, we found that by moving the sensor stack to the outside of the dome and passing a rope connected to the sensor line through the center hole instead, we could achieve the same transfer of force onto the top plate while nonetheless maintaining the ability to adapt to minor changes in angle caused by deformation of the sensor line (see Figure 3). In this configuration, it is critical for safety that the rope is secured using a robust yet easy to remove knot that can not slip through the center hole; for this purpose we used a bowline knot.¹⁶ The result of this design evolution was a sensor module that was simpler and less expensive to assemble, safer for the performer, and more robust.

Figure 5: First fully functional prototype of sensor.

¹⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bowline>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

3.3.2 Calibration Procedure. For convenience and due to time constraints, sensor calibration was performed beforehand in the lab by placing a 6 kg weight directly on top of the sensor plate according to the procedure as described in Section 3.2.3. Ideally, this step should be carried out on site by hanging much heavier test weights from sensor lines in the fully assembled dome, but as this device is not meant to be a scientific measurement instrument, some level of inaccuracy is acceptable in our application.¹⁷ Ultimately, inconsistencies in the output range from sensor to sensor are corrected for in the Max/MSP patch that receives the data, as described in Section 3.4.1; our primary concern was that the system responds in a linear manner across said range.

3.3.3 Hardware Mounting Configuration. The geodesic dome has nine sensors connected to color coded sensing lines (ratchet straps acting as makeshift slacklines) for the performer(s) to stretch, pull, hang from, and climb on, as detailed in Figures 1, 6, and 7. Each sensing line is mapped to a specific channel of the matrix routing system and uses a color coding system as a means to represent the local and remote world inputs (audio and video signals) in order to help the mixing performer(s) in the *NEXUS* (and possibly the audience) to maintain associations between the sensing lines, the mixing performance within the net of lines, and the resulting intermediary space - the virtual audio/video mix.¹⁸

The ratchet straps should be attached to the dome with the minimum amount of tension capable of supporting the performer in order to avoid deforming the load cells past their elastic limit and risking permanent damage and/or introducing a bias and thus reducing the usable output range. In the future, we will consider a four load cell system and/or adding a mechanical limit (e.g. foam spacer) to avoid overstraining the load cells. Additionally, the rigidity of the dome is maintained via the inclusion of five ropes connected across the bottommost level of ten nodes. This extra support prevents the dome from flexing under load, in turn reducing undesired coupling between sensor lines.

The M5StickC Plus's 150 mAh internal battery is only capable of regularly sending data over a wireless network for approximately one hour, so each sensor unit was hardwired to a power source via its USB-C input. It is critical that power supplies are used which are capable of providing an appropriate amount of current to the sensor unit, as under- or over-powering it seems to cause issues with the HX711 and can lead to noise spikes in the data (as described in Section 3.2.1).

Figure 6: Dome sensor line schematic specific to the kompost*klang*küche* project.

Figure 7: Final version of the dome with the optimal position of sensing lines for stability and the situated sensing line color code of the kompost*klang*küche* NIME.

¹⁷Larrieux and Roger highlight a noteworthy duality in their discussion of *scientific* and *musical instruments*, particularly those that are data-driven. The *NEXUS* (and similar NIMEs) bridges the boundary between those definitions. While the ultimate outcome is artistic, the process of generating control data to steer the system might be described as the act of "exposing hidden properties (data) of [the] environment" [26, p. 91]. This overlap is further demonstrated by the fact that many of the dimensions used in our forthcoming analysis (see Section 5.2), namely those related to sensor input and sound/image output, mirror concepts commonly considered when characterizing scientific measurement instruments.

¹⁸For additional detail on the audio and video mixing and signal flow between the locations, see 3.4.3 and [38], specifically Figure 5.

3.4 Telematic System Integration

In order to facilitate our exploration of multimedia integration across geographically disparate locations interconnected via networks, we utilized the Telemersive Toolkit [14]. This software comprises the telemersive-router and the Gateway application, both of which were developed within our research unit, the Telematic Performance Format Research Group. A suite of custom Max/MSP patches implements additional data calibration and preprocessing

stages for the *NEXUS* sensing system, manages inputs and mixing (under *NEXUS* control) of local and remote audio and video, and governs the output of multimedia streams and LED lighting configurations. The intrinsic capability of Max/MSP to manage diverse media types provides a distinct advantage in facilitating multimedia telematic performances, offering a cohesive programming environment tailored for high interactivity and integration.¹⁹

3.4.1 Sensor Data Transmission. As mentioned in Section 3.2.3, we used the shiftr.io IoT platform as a MQTT broker²⁰ for the sensor data, as it implements all necessary back-end functionality and allows for simple real-time visualization of message flow and content. Data was published to the `/load_cell_data` topic²¹ and distributed in near real-time to all subscribed clients.

Within the Max/MSP environment we created a mqtt-receive patch using `node.js` to subscribe to the `/load_cell_data` MQTT topic. When a message is received on the topic, the script splits it into separate parts, converts them into floats, and then outputs them using `maxApi.outlet`. Before it is distributed to different patches in our Max/MSP environment, the raw sensor data is first filtered and rescaled by our patch. This stage ensures that the resulting resampled data is accurate and reliable and can be further processed to generate control data for audio, video, and lighting systems.

3.4.2 Audio/Video Data Transmission. A virtual room is established in the Gateway application, wherein peers connect to share audio and video data across various channels. Access credentials, including the name and password of the room, are distributed to each user, ensuring secure entry to the session. The *NEXUS* framework is designed in such a way as to minimize the data transmitted through the Gateway and, consequently, over the internet. This goal is achieved by implementing efficient data routing strategies prior to gateway transmission (each user of the Gateway contributes just one audio and one video stream) and by managing multimedia mixing through the *NEXUS* sensor data message transmission using the MQTT protocol.²²

3.4.3 Audio/Video Mixing. As noted in Section 3.4.2, we developed an audio/visual data routing strategy within the *NEXUS* framework to optimize network usage in response to bandwidth constraints. This strategy is structured around two principal components:

- Local pre-mixing of video and audio streams facilitated by the remote *NEXUS* sensor data: by employing techniques such as superposition and blending, multiple video inputs at each location are consolidated into a single video output. This process enables the transmission of a single video and audio channel per location through the gateway;
- Implementation of a bifurcated video routing method: the mixed streams of the local video inputs are directed straight to the local video outputs, circumventing the need for internet-based transmission.

¹⁹Max/MSP by Cycling'74 - <https://cycling74.com/>, last accessed: August 12, 2024.

²⁰An MQTT broker acts as a server that facilitates message exchange between different devices and systems using the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol.

²¹MQTT topic is a string consisting of one or more levels separated by a forward slash (similar to an OSC address).

²²Additional information about the audio/video mixing and data transmission systems can be found in [38].

These strategies collectively contribute to a substantial reduction in the bandwidth required for transmitting high-quality audio/visual content, thereby ensuring efficient data flow even in environments with restricted or otherwise unreliable network capacities.

The *NEXUS*'s strategies for mixing audio and video exhibit both localized and delocalized characteristics. Namely, centralized mixing of data streams occurs within the *NEXUS* interface and its geodesic performance space, while the use of the MQTT protocol for the sensor data transmission facilitates decentralized access to the mixing data, allowing for the retrieval and preliminary processing of video and audio data at various participating locations prior to transmission through the Gateway and over the internet. This hybrid approach underscores the framework's flexibility in managing telematic performances, ensuring both centralized mixing control and distributed audio-video data stream management.

In previous analyses of the affordances of our telematic *NEXUS-NIME*, we demonstrate that our methodology transcends the mere mitigation of bandwidth constraints. It substantially enriches the telematic performance ecosystem by shifting the telematic space from realms of immersive unity to worlds of discontinuity, embracing *aesthetics of failure*, and thereby reevaluating the role of non-human actors in these spaces [38].

4 Case Study: the kompost*klang*küche*glitch* Project

The *kompost*klang*küche** project was the first use case of the *NEXUS* telematic mixing interface. It was performed during the 2023 edition of *Musikfestival Bern* from September 7-10, 2023. Feedback from performers and audience confirmed that the design objectives delineated in Section 2 were successfully achieved via the *NEXUS* framework, which facilitated the:

- a) materialization of the network-space;
- b) demonstration of the real-time agency of the media mixing engineer through a hypermediated mixing process;
- c) creation of a space of becoming in which the figure of the media messenger transforms into a performer within the telematic NIME.

Despite these achievements, the initial findings from this first case study revealed challenges in the audience's understanding of the technical operation of the *NEXUS* system and the real-time generation of the remote input streams, both of which are key aspects of the telematic assemblage. Notably, the color-coding scheme, which was designed to connect the sensing lines with the performers' inputs by correlating sensor line colors with the performers' costumes and their character names within the telematic worlding, did not communicate its intended meaning; the audience struggled to recognize the relationship between the sensing lines and their corresponding audio and video input channels. This disconnect underscores the need for a more effective communication strategy to enhance audience understanding of the interactive and interconnected aspects of the telematic NIME.

A subsequent edition of the project was performed as *kompost*klang*küche*glitch** on June 4, 2024, during the *Usinesonore Festival* at La Neuveville. In this second iteration, the audience was divided between two locations, approximately a seven-minute walk

apart. Midway through the performance, the audience swapped locations, allowing them to experience the event from both perspectives. Additionally, the sensing-line-check (rescaling), typically conducted before each rehearsal or performance (akin to a sound-check) was integrated into the performance itself. This approach made the operations of the system and the role of the mixing performers more comprehensible to the audience.

5 Analysis

In order to better understand the properties of the NEXUS's design in relation to existing digital musical instruments (DMIs) and mixing interfaces, we use a *dimension space* as tool for analysis. In 2005 Birnbaum et al. demonstrated the usefulness of dimension space analysis for “clarifying the process of [musical] device development, as each relevant characteristic [composing the system] is defined and isolated” [6, p. 195].

In their 2019 paper *Towards a Telematic Dimension Space*, Müller et al. presented a modified version of the model by Birnbaum et al. specifically designed to organize the “variety of dimensions [and technical constellations] at play in telematic performance practices” [30, p. 393]. Informed by the two aforementioned dimension space research proposals ([6], [30]) and contemporary HCI “approaches whose central metaphor is interaction as phenomenologically situated” [20, p. 9], we propose an extended version by modifying existing axes and introducing new ones.

5.1 Towards a Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction

In the following subsection we outline our approach of implementing a *phenomenological matrix* [20] into the dimension space, aiming to create a tool for the analysis of design spaces that account for *situated embodiment*.

In *Embodied Music Interaction: Creative Design Synergies Between Music Performance and HCI*, Xambó proposes characteristics of different interaction approaches to DMI design, focusing on “the role of the body” [39, p. 212] in performative settings when using such devices. She uses a table to summarize categories and compare different interaction approaches to DMI design; however, we align with Birnbaum et al., who argue that a visual representation of embodied music interaction designs better facilitates device comparison [6], allowing for the further development of interfaces and more effective “framing [of] specific questions for acute research” [30, p. 394]. Thus, we introduce Xambó's components (*body, materiality, input control, sound output, coupling physical-digital, visibility/feedback, shareability, and situatedness*) as additional dimensions on separate axis complementing the seven axes proposed by Birnbaum et al. for DMIs, sound installations, and other variants of music devices. In re-evaluating Xambó's framework for categorizing DMIs, several key adaptations were made to her components of *embodied interaction* as outlined in 5.2.

In addition to the axes proposed by Xambó, we incorporate a socially situated dimension that further augments the design space: the *Risk* axis, as articulated by Klemmer et al. [23]. The conceptual framework and the rationale for integrating this axis within the context of multimedia interactions are elaborated upon in 5.2.11.

In the context of NIME-research another fundamental modification was introduced by Müller et al. [30]: the superimposition of a scenographic/visual dimension onto the acoustic/sound dimension axis. This integration facilitates a more comprehensive analysis of NIM(ultimedia)Es, allowing for an exploration of the interconnectedness between distinct media layers, a critical feature in telematic contexts, particularly in systems such as the NEXUS. To effectively compare a variety of interaction interfaces, both local and distributed, we adopt the strategy proposed by Müller et al., where distinct plots are generated to emphasize either the acoustic layer, the scenographic layer, or a combination of both [30]. For clarity, each layer is color-coded, with the acoustic layer represented in blue and the scenographic layer in pink.

5.2 Axes Description

The subsequent descriptions of the seventeen axes within our *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction* draw upon modified models of dimension spaces developed by Birnbaum et al. [6] and Müller et al. [30]. These models have been further extended through the incorporation of considerations by Xambó [39] and Klemmer et al. [23], particularly in relation to situated and embodied design dimensions.

Figure 8: The 17-axes Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction

5.2.1 Role of Sound and Image. This axis, initially developed by Birnbaum et al., based on investigations of sound in virtual environments by Pressing [32], is further expanded in Müller et al. to include both auditory and visual dimensions. The distinct points on this axis classify the roles of sound and image, ranging from the transmission of specific *information*, to the creation of *environmental* context, to their use as mediums for *artistic expression*.

5.2.2 Audio-Visual Control. Originally conceptualized by Birnbaum et al. as *Musical Control*, the Audio-Visual Control axis has been expanded to incorporate visual dimensions, reflecting the need to address both auditory and visual aspects in interactive systems [30]. This axis consists of three discrete points, ranging from the macro level to the micro level, to describe the degree of control a user exerts over audio-visual elements. At the *process* level, control is exercised over the underlying processes that generate sound and visual content. The *note-level/frame* point represents an approach, where sound and visual content are transmitted or generated, focusing on individual notes or frames. At the opposite end of the spectrum at the *timbral/pixel* level, emphasis shifts towards the internal structure of sound or the fine details of the video image, allowing for precise manipulation of these elements.

5.2.3 Physical-Digital Coupling [Latency]. Building on Xambó's criteria, the Physical-Digital Coupling axis examines the degree of coherence of the integration between physical interactions and their corresponding digital responses within DMIs and other interactive systems. This axis is particularly concerned with latency, the delay between a physical action and its digital response [39]. That said, all actions, whether digital or strictly existing in the analog world, incur some amount of latency between action and perception, the more important question is if that time delay is larger than what our perceptual systems are able to integrate as *real-time* or not. Müller et al. point out that the concept of real-time systems is generally problematic in telematic performances, as (perceived) perfect synchronicity across locations is typically unattainable due to the inherent latency, the unavoidable delay in signal transmission between sender and receiver. They suggest organizing this axis based on the performers' approaches to managing latency, ranging from *ignoring*, to *tolerating*, to *accepting* it. While this is an interesting approach, in the context of this study, which compares local *and* distributed interface designs, such an arrangement is less applicable; instead, the axis is structured according to the more traditional degree of perceivable latency measurement.

5.2.4 Degrees of Freedom [Input]. Xambó's *Input Control* category was omitted due to its overlap with both Materiality and Interaction Approaches. Instead of focusing on specific technologies (e.g., sensors, multitouch surfaces), we retained the Degrees of Freedom axis, which allows for a more generalized comparison of interactive capabilities across different devices. This approach shifts the focus from the technical specifics to the broader interactive potential of the systems, making the dimension space model more adaptable and relevant across various contexts. While Degrees of Freedom often refers to the number of independent movements and orientations that an input device can detect in this context, (e.g. lateral movements along the X, Y, and Z axes, and rotational movements around these axes), we extend the concept to also reflect the range of input controls available to a user within a multimedial system, extending continuously from devices with minimal input options to those offering a multitude of controls.

5.2.5 Feedback Modalities [Outputs]. The Feedback Modalities axis represents the range of feedback mechanisms provided by a system, extending from *monomodal* to *multimodal* outputs, including visual, auditory, and haptic feedback, which Bongers describes in terms of

force, texture, and shape [3]. Originally proposed by Birnbaum et al., this axis captures the degree to which a system offers feedback to the user, and is, in a sense, the counterpoint to the Degrees of Freedom [Input] axis. Bongers further differentiates between active feedback, where the system generates forces or vibrations in response to user input, and passive feedback, which is inherent to the physical properties of the interface, such as the resistance felt when pressing a piano key.

5.2.6 Movement Topology. As Müller et al. note, the interaction between human actors and technical interfaces is not solely defined by nature of their interactions or the number of participants, but also by the topological arrangement of components, such as screens, loudspeakers, and other material carriers of representation. As such, independent of the specific interaction modalities an interactive system provides, we add a Movement Topology axis to our dimension space, thus enabling the comparison of systems based on their physical movement capabilities, such as those captured by Xambó's *mobile* modality. Building upon Müller et al.'s Movement Topology axis, the dimension reflects the spatial and dynamic characteristics of interactive systems along a continuum from *static* to *dynamic*. In the context of a *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction* applicable to both local and distributed interfaces, the inclusion of Movement Topology as a distinct category enriches the result by highlighting the relationship between spatial arrangement and interaction, offering insights into how mobility and physical positioning influence user experience, bodily presence, and the virtualization of interactions in embodied multimedial interfaces.

5.2.7 Audio-Visual Output. Expanding on Xambó's concept of *Sound Output*, this axis is extended to encompass Visual Output, addressing the delivery of both audio and video information. It spans from *embedded* systems, where audio and visual outputs are fully integrated within a self-contained system, to *detached* systems, in which sound and video outputs are separate from the input control, thereby facilitating the consideration of stereo or multichannel sound amplification configurations.

5.2.8 Materiality. We organized the Materiality axis along a continuum from *digital* to *analog*, specifically ranging from abstract, digital interfaces (e.g., screen-based) to physically more substantial interfaces (e.g., *seemingly* analog objects).

5.2.9 Interaction Modality. Overlaps in multiple categories proposed by Xambó, namely *Interaction Approaches* and *Materiality* (e.g. the dual use of the term *wearable*), underscored the necessity for further refinement to eliminate conceptual ambiguity and ensure that each category serves a distinct and precise function within the dimension space model. Thus, the Interaction Approaches category, which originally included both interaction modalities (e.g., tangible, gesture-based) and device form factors (e.g., mobile, laptop-based), was refined to focus solely on the nature of user engagement, represented along a continuous axis from *gestural* to *tangible* interactions. Specific device types, such as laptops, were excluded from this axis to avoid redundancy and maintain a clear distinction between interaction modalities and form factors.

5.2.10 Body. Building on Xambó, who references Bongers's *Range* dimension [3], this axis delineates the extent of bodily involvement

in interaction, ranging from highly *localized* engagement on one end of the spectrum (e.g. interaction via the hands or mouth only) and extending to *full-body* participation on the other.

5.2.11 Risk. The inclusion of a supplementary Risk axis in the dimension space introduces a critical dimension that encapsulates the potential for error or failure during interaction, spanning physical, social, and technological risks. This dimension, originally proposed by Klemmer et al., captures the inherent uncertainties of interaction, where actions may lead to unpredictable outcomes that cannot be easily reversed. In social contexts, the notion of risk extends beyond physical harm to encompass the pressures of performing in the presence of others, where the stakes are both personal and interpersonal. It also acknowledges the dual nature of risk: while it can heighten anxiety and challenge, it also creates opportunities for more trusting, committed, and focused interactions.

5.2.12 Situatedness. The Situatedness axis captures the degree to which interaction within a DMI or other interactive system is influenced by the specific context in which it occurs. Drawing on Xambó's interpretation of Suchman [35], it refers to how users, whether individuals or groups, construct shared meanings through their interactions with technology in a given context. This dimension recognizes that the meaning and effectiveness of an interaction are not only shaped by the technology itself, but also by the social and environmental circumstances surrounding its use. The degree of Situatedness varies from *low*, where interactions are relatively decontextualized, to *high*, where context plays a critical role in shaping the interaction. This perspective is particularly relevant when considering both performers and audiences, as the context can significantly impact the experience and interpretation of the interaction, depending on the specific technology and the people involved. Consequently, the context may lead to differing interpretations and experiences between performers and the audience, underscoring the importance of clarifying the perspective being considered when analyzing Situatedness.

5.2.13 Media Transparency [Visibility; Awareness]. In reconsidering Xambó's notion of *Visibility/Clarity*, which addresses the perception of performers' actions by others, we suggest a shift in focus. Her analysis already partially accounts for the visibility of performers' actions through the Body axis, where she observes that "the greater the human body scale used, the more visible and clear it will be for other group members and for the audience" [39, p. 216]. Given that this aspect of visibility is sufficiently covered by the body axis, we argue that it would be more valuable to direct attention to the visibility - or opacity - of the apparatus or medium itself. Müller et al. introduce the axis *Media Transparency* in their Telematic Dimension Space to distinguish "between approaches that operate in an immersive," invisible, immediate, *transparent* way and those that engage with the meaning of the interface, thus "making the medium itself perceivable, tangible," [30, p. 395] or *opaque* (hypermediated). While this concept is particularly relevant when considering telematic NIMEs, we extend it to other interfaces for embodied multimedial interaction, where complex interactions between the user, technology, and media content are common.

5.2.14 Distribution in Space. The Distribution in Space dimension, as proposed by Birnbaum, remains applicable without modification

for the purposes of this paper. The axis represents the extent of the physical area encompassed by the interaction, ranging from *local* to globally *distributed* spaces. This axis provides a framework for analyzing how the spatial reach of an interaction influences both the design and the experience of the interactive system, accommodating scenarios from intimate, co-located interactions to complex, telematic performances across multiple geographical locations.

5.2.15 Inter-actors [Shareability]. The Inter-actors axis reflects the number of individuals involved in a musical or interactive experience. Originally conceptualized by Birnbaum et al., this axis aligns with Xambó's concept of *Shareability* and captures the spectrum of interaction, from *single-user* interfaces typical of traditional musical instruments to DMIs to installations designed for *collaborative* use, where multiple participants can interact simultaneously.

5.2.16 Media Agency. To facilitate a comparative analysis of local and telematic mixing interfaces alongside installations and musical instruments (e.g. *Global String* and *SoundNet*, as introduced in Section 5.3), we introduce a Media Agency axis. This dimension represents a continuum ranging from *controller* to *instrument*, enabling a more nuanced examination of the varying degrees of agency embodied by different media forms.

5.2.17 Required Expertise. The Required Expertise axis represents the level of practice, familiarity, and expertise necessary for a user or performer to interact effectively with a DMI or interactive system. As described by Birnbaum et al., this axis is continuous, ranging from *low* to *high* expertise. At the low end, minimal prior experience is needed, such as in simple interactions where users can engage with the system with little to no specialized knowledge. On the high end, advanced expertise is required, where users, such as instrumentalists, electro-acousticians, or dancers, must develop and refine specialized skills to fully utilize the system's capabilities [30].

5.3 Historical Contextualization of the NEXUS Instrument Design

Inspired by Tanaka's explorations in [37], the *NEXUS* further develops several related concepts. Two instrument designs are key to a comparison with the *NEXUS* instrument design: *Global String* and *Soundnet*.²³

In *Global String*, Tanaka and Toeplitz present a multi-site networked music installation with physical strings at each site that links to a virtual string that spans the globe to enable collaborative performances. Sensorband's (Ata Tanaka, Zbigniew Karkowski, Edwin van der Heide) multi-user instrument *Soundnet* (1995) (inspired by *The Web*, a 1 meter diameter spider's web created by Michel Waisvisz, at STEIM [24]) is a large-scale, multi-user sensor instrument (sensor design by Bert Bongers and fabrication by Theo Borsboom) that physically engages performers through a large scale web-like plane structure, allowing them to modulate sound via control of filter and granular synthesis parameters by climbing and interacting with the two dimensional web. Sensorband combines physical structure, sensor technology, and digital signal processing

²³For descriptions of the musical instruments, see [4], [37], [3], [5].

to create a sound-making object that is both played and inhabited locally.

While *Soundnet* emphasizes physical presence and the interconnectivity of performers within a shared space, the *NEXUS* extends these concepts into the telematic realm, integrating sensor-augmented environments to facilitate networked performances that bridge geographical distances. We argue that the idea of a globe-spanning telematic line (*Global String*) and a large-scale physical-mechanical sensor-augmented web (*Soundnet*) are combined in the *NEXUS*, resulting in a three-dimensional novel networked multimedia mixing console.

5.4 Dimension Space Analysis

In order to comprehensively evaluate our work in relation to the two aforementioned historical instruments, we present a dimension space analysis of *Soundnet*, *Global String*, and the telematic *NEXUS* using our *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction*.

5.4.1 Soundnet. *Soundnet* comprises both a net and an expressive interactive musical system that functions on an architectural scale. The system’s design facilitates a multi-user environment characterized by *full-body* engagement, with performers physically interacting with a large, tangible structure. The *degree of freedom* afforded to the performers is extensive, as the system responds to a wide range of physical inputs, including climbing, pulling, and manipulating the interconnected ropes. This level of interaction underscores the system’s emphasis on tangible interaction modalities and places *Soundnet* on the analog end of the *materiality* spectrum. *Control* within *Soundnet* operates primarily at the process level; performers’ broad, physical movements influence the overall sound generated and are less suited for micro-level manipulations. This approach aligns with the large-scale, interconnected nature of the system, where the physical actions of one performer can unpredictably affect the entire structure, creating a dynamic and somewhat uncontrollable performance environment.

Feedback in *Soundnet* is predominantly auditory and haptic. The performers receive immediate tactile passive feedback through the tension and movement of the ropes, coupled with auditory feedback from the sounds produced. The system’s design, however, does not emphasize visual feedback. The physicality of the interaction, combined with the static yet dynamic *movement topology* of the system, requires performers to engage their entire bodies, introducing a degree of physical *risk*, coupled with the social dynamics inherent in multi-performer interaction.

Given its large-scale architectural nature, *Soundnet* is a *moderately situated* system, as the action of performers interacting with the instrument are heavily influenced by the web-like spatial configuration of the ropes and their interactions with one another. However, as it is typically employed in performance contexts where the environment is relatively standardized, the primary emphasis placed on the interaction between the musician and the instrument rather than the surrounding space. In this context, situated elements, such as the social dynamics of the audience, play a secondary role in shaping the overall experience.

Even if the underlying process of sound production remains obscure and difficult for the audience to discern, the physical structure

of *Soundnet* is prominently visible and plays an integral role in the performance, ensuring that the medium itself is not concealed.

Soundnet demands a relatively high *level of expertise* from its performers, necessitating both physical skill and a familiarity with the system’s intricate dynamics.

Figure 9: *Soundnet* dimension space analysis.

5.4.2 Global String. *Global String* is a telematic installation that integrates both audio and visual layers to create a phenomenologically situated networked musical experience. The audio component, acting as the leading layer, is deeply *embedded* within the interactive system, with sound serving as the primary medium for artistic expression and collaboration across globally distributed sites. The interaction with the global physical string requires *full-body* engagement and generates sound through the physical-virtual networked string, placing the audio layer on the tangible end of the *interaction modality* spectrum. The video layer, while providing essential visual *feedback* (in addition to the sonic and haptic feedback from the leading layer) and context, operates more as a supplementary tool and is therefore positioned closer to the *gestural* end of the spectrum.

The installation’s *audio-visual output* reflects a contrast between the embedded nature of the audio, and the more detached nature of the video, which supports the interaction on an informational (real-time visualizations of the waveform of string synthesis) and environmental (video conferencing projection for remote communication between participants) level.

Global String embraces *latency* as an integral part of the experience, and its networked design necessitates a moderate *level of expertise* from performers, who must navigate the complexities of remote collaboration. While the installation is globally *distributed*, the interaction is highly *situated*, with the meaning and experience shaped by the specific physical and social contexts of each site. In the *media transparency* dimension *Global String* aims to create the illusion of continuity across locations, yet simultaneously reveals its own mediality through the inherent artificiality of the arrangement.

Figure 10: Global String dimension space analysis - acoustic layer [blue], video layer [pink], (overlap shows as [lavender]).

5.4.3 *NEXUS*. Grounded in a comparative examination with *Soundnet* and *Global String*, the dimension space analysis of the *NEXUS* telematic Novel Mixing-Interface for Multimedial Exploration, reveals several critical distinctions and convergences, particularly concerning materiality, interaction modality, situatedness, and media agency.

Similar to *Soundnet*, the *NEXUS* prioritizes physical interaction within a large-scale structure, emphasizing the importance of materiality. In *Soundnet*, the physical engagement of performers with a web of ropes is central to the system’s design, resulting in a tangible and immersive experience. Similarly, the *NEXUS* transforms the traditional mixing console into a physical-semiotic web within a geodesic dome, where performers manipulate sensor lines to influence multimedia streams. This approach aligns with the embodied interaction paradigm, making the interaction modality in both systems highly tangible; however, the *NEXUS* further incorporates a telematic dimension, linking multiple geographical locations and thus extending the interaction space into the virtual realm, thus more closely aligning it with *Global String*.

Global String relies upon balances between tangible and digital interaction, so while the physical manipulation of the string serves as the primary interface, much of the interaction occurs within the virtual networked space, reflecting a hybrid materiality that straddles both dimension and digital domains. This dual nature contrasts with the *NEXUS*’s more explicit focus on materializing the virtual network in a physical space, thus enhancing the performers’ awareness of the telecommunication infrastructure.

The *NEXUS* and *Global String* both emphasize the significance of situatedness, though they do so in different ways. *Global String* creates a networked auditory space that links geographically distant performers, making the interaction highly dependent on the specific physical and social contexts of each site. The latency inherent in this networked interaction is embraced as part of the creative

process, positioning the system as an exploration of telematic performance across spaces. *Situatedness* is equally important in the *NEXUS*, but takes on a more architectural dimension. The geodesic dome not only serves as the physical interface but also materializes the intermediary space between distant locations, making the telematic network itself a tangible, interactive environment. This approach enhances the performers’ and audience’s awareness of the medium’s agency. However, the situated nature of action between the *NEXUS* mixing interface, the mixing performers and their environment and social context must be deliberately constructed in every use-case; it is not inherently present. In the context of *Soundnet*, on the other hand, situatedness is limited to the performers and their immediate local environment of the installation.

The *NEXUS* and *Soundnet* differ significantly in their approach to media transparency. In the *NEXUS*, the medium is intentionally made visible and its agency explored through the design of the interface, aligning with the concept of hypermediacy. *Soundnet*, on the other hand, exhibits lower media transparency; the underlying process of sound production remains opaque to the audience, focusing more on the physical interaction than on revealing the mediation process.

In terms of risk, both the *NEXUS* and *Soundnet* emphasize physical engagement, with each system introducing significant physical risk due to the performative interaction with large-scale, tangible structures. While technologies of telepresence and digital design tools typically aim to minimize or eliminate risk [23], the *NEXUS* deliberately reintroduces risk across multiple dimensions. Physically, the 3-dimensional climbing dome poses challenges for the performers; socially, the opacity of their mediating actions heightens uncertainty; and technically, the lack of pre-monitoring for remote inputs, along with the potential for glitches and drop-outs inherent in telecommunication technologies further amplify the inherent risks within the system. *Global String*, while involving lower physical risk, also includes social and technical risks related to the challenges of remote collaboration and networked performance, particularly due to the potential for latency and communication breakdowns.

In summary, the *NEXUS* offers a unique blend of real-digital interaction, materializing the telematic network within an architectural space, and emphasizing the visibility and agency of the medium.

6 Discussion

Building upon the preceding presentation of specific dimension space plots, we now explore the trends and underlying structures that the dimension space framework reveals when applied to various NIMEs. By analyzing these systems, we aim to demonstrate that our adapted model of a *Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction* serves as an effective analytical tool for existing interface designs and provides a valuable framework for the further development of Novel Interfaces for Multimedial Exploration.

Through the lens of the dimension space plot, we critically assess the social and technical dynamics at play within the *NEXUS* systems, focusing on how embodied interaction, contextual sensitivity, and the interplay between opacity and transparency ultimately shape

Figure 11: NEXUS dimension space analysis - acoustic layer [blue], video layer [pink], (overlap shows as [lavender]).

the user experience and the role of the mixing engineer in telematic and participatory contexts.

6.1 Dimension Space Trends

As Birnbaum et al. [6] and Müller et al. [30] have demonstrated, dimension space plots offer the capacity to reveal underlying trends and structures of NIMEs through their visual representation. In our analysis we observed three notable groupings of components, presented below.

The NEXUS and Soundnet both feature large coverage in the lower left region of the plots, a result that aligns with the strong emphasis these NIMEs place on embodied interface manipulation. We therefore group the axes concerned (Materiality, Interaction Modality, Body, and Risk) into *Embodied Interaction* Components (see Figure 8).

Another grouping appears in the comparison of Global String and the NEXUS with high values at the mid-left side of the plot. The Risk, Situatedness, and Media Transparency axes do not align neatly with traditional quantifiable evaluation framework, rather they resonate with the third paradigm of HCI design [20], where “notions of culture, emotion, reflexivity and multiple mediation have entered center stage” [33, p. 12]. In this context, the evaluation of what makes a system successful must consider context-specific and subjective factors, rather than relying solely on universally valid measures [20]. We therefore group these dimensions into *Soft Criteria* components (see Figure 8). In our model the *Embodied Interaction* and the *Soft Criteria* components are sequentially aligned, overlapping at the Risk dimension.

Finally, a third overarching category, *Contextual Application* (Media Transparency, Distribution in Space, Inter-actors, Media Agency, Required Expertise), primarily drawn from Birnbaum’s dimension space analysis, identifies trends in the visual representation of diverse design contexts, such as installations or performance settings.

Our analysis of Soundnet, Global String and the NEXUS reveals distinct patterns in their dimension space plots, notably around the axes related to physical embodiment and soft, context-sensitive criteria. Additionally, the insights gained from our analysis underscore the value of the extended dimension space framework introduced in this paper. By integrating components such as *Embodied Interaction* and *Soft Criteria* into our dimension space, we have been able to highlight critical aspects of interaction design that are often overlooked in traditional frameworks.

6.2 The Multi-User NEXUS-NIME

Having identified foundational trends within our dimension space framework, we turn to the specific application of this analysis: the NEXUS-NIME. In our use case of the kompost*klang*küche* NIME, the novel, large-scale, sensor-augmented NEXUS is programmed to serve as mixing device in the telematic ecosystem and represents a large-scale X [Interface].

Unlike in the traditional field of live sound engineering, where the sound mixing engineer “and their labor are intricately bound to the illusion of transparency” [34, p. 31], the dimension space plot for the NEXUS reveals a contrasting paradigm: it is highly visible as an architectural space, exhibits opacity in media transparency, and is characterized by embodied interaction, where mixing agents engage their entire bodies in the operation of the instrument. This increased visibility and embodiment fundamentally shifts the social position of the mixing engineer, moving away from the approach of the concert-mixing laborer committed to what Slaten terms *social fidelity* [34], a concept that describes the expectations placed upon engineers within classical live sound mixing contexts. This concept highlights the engineer’s commitment to establishing trust with performers and aligning their mixing practice with the performers’ artistic vision, thereby ensuring fidelity in sound transmission. By making the implications of the media mixing agents actions more visible (to the audience) and increasing risk in the context of distant telematic mixing, the NEXUS enhances the mixing engineer’s awareness, commitment and their sense of “responsibility for decisions, helping to overcome the human inclination for obedience to authority” [23, p. 7]. This heightened sense of agency of the media mixing performer with their X [Instrument] is particularly crucial in this risky relational field of the NEXUS. Here the human-machine interface operates as both a multi-user X [Medium] and [Interface] emphasizing a circular dependency: mixing agents rely on the video and audio material sent by the other nodes (other performers) in the network, while these performers depend on the mediating labor of the mixing agents within the sensing X [performance Space].

Walter et al. reveal the inherent aesthetics of failure within telematic performance contexts by analyzing diverse networked systems employed for multimedial explorations across various artistic fields [38]. In their initial examination of the kompost*klang*küche* project, they demonstrate that through a *discontinuity approach* and the manifestation of glitches, the network itself emerges as an active participant, disrupting the spatial continuity of the telematic world and rendering media transmission opaque. As a result of these *breakdown situations*, another significant actor and variable in the NEXUS-NIME emerges in the world: the X [Network] itself.

In light of these interdependencies, we propose a reframing of the relational dynamic of the *NEXUS* telematic performance system and its design through the lens of feminist new materialism and posthumanism. This approach emphasizes *rendering-capable* and *becoming-with*, concepts that emphasize the cultivation of *response-ability*, the capacity to respond (as discussed by Haraway [18], referring to Despret [10], [11]) in a human-machine entanglement. "Response-ability [...] requires the risk of being for some worlds rather than others and helping to compose those worlds with others." [18, p. 178]

Given these insights into how the *NEXUS* operates as a multi-user, sensor-augmented interface within a larger telematic ecosystem, departing from traditional paradigms of live sound engineering, the next steps in our research will focus on further exploring these emergent dynamics and expanding the application of the *NEXUS* beyond its current context.

6.3 Future Work

Future research directions will focus on exploring the evolving role of the mixing engineer within telematic performance ecosystems and the *NEXUS*'s capabilities navigating the continuum between opacity and transparency in media transmission.

Furthermore, the utility of the *NEXUS* will be extended beyond performance applications to include educational settings and telematic participatory installations, broadening the scope of its applicability. In this context, the dimension space analysis by Birnbaum et al. demonstrates that installations typically involve a higher number of participants at the point of interaction, often with the expectation that these participants are non-experts [6]. By comparing the *NEXUS* with systems like *Global String* and *Soundnet*, it becomes evident that the *NEXUS* occupies a central position on the Media Agency axis, suggesting a balanced integration of human and technological agency within the system. This central positioning highlights the *NEXUS*'s unique capacity to operate effectively in both performative and installation contexts. While the *NEXUS* was originally designed for telematic performance, its potential as a tool in participatory installations is significant, particularly within the multi-user paradigm. The flexibility of the *NEXUS*, allowing for both expert and non-expert interactions, underscores its capability to facilitate collaborative and participatory experiences across a range of environments. Explorations of the *NEXUS*'s capabilities in non-telematic NIMEs, particularly in local media mixing, sound spatialization, and synthesis, promise to expand the horizons of musical lutherie and performance.

7 Conclusions

This study has explored the design and application of the *Nexus*, our Telematic Novel Mixing-Interface for Multimedial Exploration, within the broader context of telematic performance practices. Through an approach grounded in the principles of embodied interaction and phenomenology, we have developed a novel interface that extends the range of the tabletop multimedia mixing practice into the architectural and telematic space, connecting dispersed geographical locations.

Central to our research was the development of a tool for the visual representation of embodied interaction designs, namely the

Dimension Space for Phenomenologically Situated Interaction. Our design space encapsulates components of interaction design that are often overlooked in conventional frameworks, particularly the interplay between embodiment, risk, and media transparency. Through a comparative dimension space analysis juxtaposing the *NEXUS* with historical interfaces for (networked and local) musical and multimedial expression, pioneered by Sensorband, Atau Tanaka, and Bert Bongers, we have identified foundational trends that resonate with the third paradigm of HCI design.

Our findings demonstrate that by foregrounding the role of the entire body of the media mixing performer within a situated multi-user sensor-based system, we are able to reframe conventional sound engineering practices. Our *NEXUS*-NIME offers a novel paradigm where the role of the mixing engineer shifts from one centered on transparency and social fidelity, to one characterized by heightened awareness, visibility and hypermediacy.

The design of the telematic *NEXUS*-NIME system accentuates the risky relational field of interactions between the human mixing agents and the networked system, emphasizing the mutual dependency among performers, the human-machine interface, and the network itself as entities that are *rendering-capable* and engaged in *becoming-with*. A reframing of the material-semiotic web through the lenses of feminist new materialism and posthumanism underscores the concept of *response-ability*, highlighting the ethical responsibility of co-composing worlds with heterogeneous actors within the telematic space. Future research will aim to further explore these emergent dynamics and to extend the application of the *NEXUS*-NIME beyond its current telematic context.

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²⁴<https://worldingmycelium.space/>

²⁵<https://networkperformance.space/>

²⁶The research project group consists of Patrick Müller, Benjamin Burger, Joel De Giovanni, Martin Fröhlich, Roman Haefeli, Eric Larrieux, Johannes Schütt, Hannah "Vyborg" Walter and Matthias Ziegler

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